

SEEING THROUGH DEFORMED LUNAR CRUST: EARTH'S ANORTHOSITE AS A KEY.

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Introduction: Lunar anorthosites predominantly formed through the flotation of plagioclase crystals within the lunar magma ocean (LMO), establishing the primary crust [1]. However, since their formation, the lunar crust and its anorthosites have been significantly altered by meteorite impacts, the most prevalent secondary process affecting planetary surfaces. These impacts led to the heavily cratered appearance of the lunar highlands, widespread brecciation and significant modifications at the micrometre scale. This extensive deformation complicates the analysis of the pristine magmatic records within these rocks. For instance, studying shock-deformed anorthosites is essential to compare remotely detected anorthosites with those found in meteorite and Apollo collections and to ascertain their lateral and vertical distribution within the lunar crust [1]. Additionally, impact-induced deformation significantly alters the radiometric ages of lunar samples [2], thereby complicating the reconstruction of the timing and sequence of crustal solidification. Understanding these secondary – deformation – effects is crucial for a comprehensive assessment of lunar crust formation, yet this aspect remains underexplored, representing a significant caveat in our current knowledge of lunar anorthosites.

Motivation: While the geochemical properties of terrestrial and lunar anorthosites have been somewhat compared [3], their microstructural properties remain largely underexplored. We propose a collaborative study comparing lunar, Apollo mission-collected anorthosites with 1) well-characterized terrestrial analogues, on Lofoten-Vesteraalen islands, Norway and 2) newly obtained anorthosites through the DIVE drilling project (<http://dive2ivrea.org>) through deep-crustal sequence of rocks in the Ivrea-Verbano Zone, Italy. The Lofoten terrestrial anorthosites provide an ideal comparison, as they represent massive, dry, plagioclase-rich formations that have been locally subject to high strain rate events. In addition, they are very well exposed, with continuous outcrop from no strain to very high strain [4], allowing to study the increased signature of deformation on pristine plagioclase. Studying microstructure and composition of newly obtained IVZ core samples allows for unique advantages as they formed in sequence with increasing depth, and therefore mimic systematic changes in formation conditions.

Objectives and methods: Apollo anorthosites, often found as brecciated fragments atop the lunar regolith, exhibit complex, polygenetic geological

histories that complicate the interpretation of their primary magmatic origins. By examining terrestrial anorthosites from well-established geological contexts, we aim to develop methodologies and process understanding for identifying secondary deformation and disentangling the complex histories preserved in lunar samples. Our objectives are:

- 1) to systematically study the microstructures and composition of undeformed (fresh), mildly, and significantly deformed anorthosites from the Lofoten and IVZ using Scanning Electron Microscopy, Electron Backscatter Diffraction and Transmission Kikuchi Diffraction [5].
- 2) to use these simpler terrestrial analogues to interpret the complex, variably deformed lunar anorthosites. We will perform exploratory microstructural analyses of lunar anorthosites from Apollo 15 and 17 missions, on which we have previously worked or we recently obtained from the ExMAG.

At the upcoming ELS meeting, we aim at presenting methodology and preliminary data on some of the collected samples.

References: [1] Elardo et al., 2023. *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* 89, 293–338. [2] Černok et al. 2021 *Commun. Earth Environ.* 2, 1–9. [3] Sotiriou, P. et al., 2024. *Geosci. Front.* 101914 [4] Markl, Frost and Bucher 1998. *Journal of Petrology*, 39(8), 1425-1452 [5] Piazzolo et al. (2016) *Nat Commun* 7, 10490.

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